

IMPROVING STUDENTS' PERFORMANCE OF PRACTICAL TASKS USING INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TECHNOLOGY LESSONS.

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Abstract. In the article, thoughts and opinions about the implementation of practical tasks for students of technology science using interactive methods are highlighted.

In technology classes, it is explained how to comply with technical safety rules, the correct use of technological maps, drawings, tables, schemes, dimensions, and interactive methods necessary to perform practical tasks.

Key words: lesson, training, goal, ability, interactive, technology, practical, assignment, education, material, method, independent, technique.

Attention to the creation of interesting and effective types of pedagogical technologies for application to the educational process in every educational environment is developing day by day. One of the main reasons for this is that in the past, in traditional education, students were taught to acquire only ready-made knowledge, but with the help of modern technologies, they find the knowledge they are acquiring by themselves. It teaches them to independently study and analyze the topics covered, and even draw their own conclusions. In this process, the teacher creates conditions for students' intellectual development, formation of thinking, learning and education, and thus occupies the main place in educational processes.

In technology classes, the science teacher performs tasks aimed at organizing and managing modern educational activities, promoting a healthy lifestyle among students, and teaching the subject with interesting methods. At the same time, students' skills to perform practical tasks are developed while strengthening their knowledge.

In order to fully fulfill this task, first of all, scientists and researchers should find solutions to several problems in cooperation with teachers of technology science working in general education schools. In particular, in teaching technology, teachers should pay close attention to the following:

Identifying the essence of pedagogical technology, interactive methods and creating its theoretical and practical foundations;

development of its scientific principles;

choosing and implementing effective ways to implement interactive methods.

What are interactive methods? Although there are several answers to the question of why a new approach to the design of the educational process is needed, it is necessary to use their improved methods for classroom and extracurricular activities.

One of the most important achievements of pedagogical technology for interactive methods is the creation of a fund of tests, a set of checks that fully cover the progress of the educational process, and several types of practical tasks. For 9th grade students of technology science, it is very convenient to perform practical tasks in class along with pre-prepared, standardized tests. Students should perform practical tasks with the correct use of technological maps, drawings, tables, schemes, dimensions and interactive methods, while following the rules of technical safety in mastering each educational material, as well as rapid feedback in evaluation allows installation. Directs the educational process towards the set goal.

Choosing active teaching methods

When choosing and implementing technology elements in education, it is necessary to take into account the learning activities of students. In the first 20 minutes of practical lessons in technology, new knowledge is given to students, and then the given knowledge is strengthened through the implementation of debates, working in small groups and other such non-traditional methods. In addition, it is necessary to choose interactive methods that will provide a basis for effective teaching in order to develop students' performance of practical tasks.

The goal of any education is to develop and apply quality instruction necessary to develop knowledge, skills, and competencies.

Pedagogical technology interactive methods are defined as the use of technical tools, computer, distance learning or various techniques that need to be used in the teaching process in connection with information technology. From the subject of technology, each lesson has its own technology of the educational subject, that is, pedagogical technology in the educational process is an individual process, which is directed to one goal, based on the needs of the student, designed in advance and is a pedagogical process aimed at providing a guaranteed result.

It is known that one of the modern methods of new pedagogical technology is a lesson conducted using interactive methods with the help of a computer. The advantage of the computer-written lesson program is that the student is clearly familiar with a realistic dynamic model of complex processes on the subject. In

other methods of teaching, the student does not have this opportunity, but another problem is that not all schools have enough computer equipment. Interactive methods should be used to solve such problems.

In order to activate the 9th grade students in technology, we use new types of interactive methods to perform practical tasks. They include: "Game technology", "Networks" cluster method, "Boomerang", "Scorabey", "Libra", "Fan", "Golden hand" technologies and others. Which interactive method to choose for a lesson depends on the characteristics of the subject and the subject in it.

For example, the "Golden hand" technology is considered one of the effective methods in the educational process. Its task is to encourage students to actively learn and develop the skills of performing practical tasks in their thinking. "Golden Hand" is creative, active, capable and suitable for students' goals of making new items with their own hands. The advantage of this technology is that it primarily develops the independent, mental activity of the student. Pupils are taught to prepare an item, to express their ideas with their own hands, that is, to work actively. In this place, every student is encouraged to perform practical tasks freely. In this way, consistency is freely demonstrated, first of all, even when a problematic situation arises, students can independently complete practical tasks. Then the students' skills develop during the learning process. Also, the advantage of this technology is that the student has a good understanding of the subject in the educational and educational function.

"Golden hand" technology

"Golden hand" technology creates a great opportunity for students to consciously and firmly acquire knowledge, to determine their active attitude to the environment, and to revive cognitive activity. In this process, the teacher helps the students to organize the activities of performing the given practical tasks. Only then, based on the analysis of topics, students will independently solve intellectual problems, draw conclusions and generalize, and try to apply the acquired knowledge to a new situation.

In short, it is appropriate to use various methods to make the process of teaching 9th grade students effective. In order to ensure the quality of teaching in the classroom, the teacher can also organize activities outside the classroom in order to deepen and expand the knowledge of the topics mastered by the students. The effectiveness of the events depends on the perfect preparation of the students and the development of the skills to perform the given practical tasks.

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